

D2.2 Catalog of Metadata Standards Relevant to NFDI

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About

PID4NFDI (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through Base4NFDI.

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Introduction

The initialisation phase of the PID4NFDI project is dedicated to establishing a comprehensive understanding of the persistent identifier (PID) landscape within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). As part of the deliverables for work package 2 (WP2) in the initialization phase, this document serves as deliverable D2.2 *Catalog of Metadata Standards Relevant to NFDI*.

The aim of WP2 was to develop concepts for technical implementation of PID services and interoperability. The focus is thereby on topics such as metadata interoperability and harmonisation. In this framework, a catalog of metadata standards, groups, and mappings that are actively used in NFDI is valuable for two main reasons. For one thing, it serves as an **overview for the PID4NFDI team**, allowing a better understanding of the dispersed NFDI service landscape and identification of standards in use. This in turn helps to develop metadata harmonisation and interoperability approaches that address the complex and specific metadata requirements of NFDI consortia. For another thing, such a catalog can act as **guidance for stakeholders** to address questions around metadata standards (see also the section *Scope of the Catalog* to distinguish which of those questions are immediately addressed by the current version of the catalog), for example:

- “I want to develop a service and I am looking for a discipline specific or generic metadata standard to use. Which standards are used in NFDI by the other consortia and by which specific services? Which are the most popular standards used within NFDI? If I decide for standard X, which other services or consortia will my service be interoperable with, such that data can flow seamlessly between them?”
- “I am not sure which PID provider my organization should work with. Which provider has its own metadata schema and where can I find it? Do they have a mapping I can use?”
- “I am interested in joining a metadata group. Which groups do other NFDI consortia engage with and are those groups discussing discipline specific metadata issues?”
- “Where can I find the latest version and specifications of metadata standards? Is the standard regularly updated or is the latest version already some years old?”

Access the Catalog: [Catalog of Metadata Standards](#)

Scope of the Catalog

Description of the Tables

The catalog currently constitutes three tables:

- 1. Metadata Standards:** The table lists metadata standards used in the NFDI. For each standard, the discipline in which it is applied, the webpage, the version number and release date, the link to the specification, and a description are given. Additional information may be available (e.g. links to other metadata catalogues where the standard is also listed, with further useful information). A list of consortia which use the standard is provided, to be updated over time.
- 2. PID Provider metadata schemas:** The table contains the name of the PID provider, the webpage, and whether the PID provider has a fixed schema. If the PID provider has a fixed schema, the current version, the release date, and the specification of the schema are displayed.
- 3. Metadata Groups:** The table contains the name of the metadata group, its focus (discipline, topics, resources), the webpage, involved NFDI consortia, and a description.

Knowledge Base

The standards and groups listed in the table were identified based on two surveys: The first one was conducted in 2023 by the *NFDI working group on Persistent Identifier Services* in preparation of the PID4NFDI project [1]. The second one, titled *Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services*, was conducted in April 2024 as part of the PID4NFDI project [2]. Both surveys targeted infrastructure managers of NFDI services and consortia representatives with responsibilities in PID management. In both surveys, participants were asked which standards, mappings, and extensions are applied in their repositories, and which metadata groups they are involved in. The results reveal a large variety of applied standards, customised metadata schemas, mappings, and involvement in metadata groups:

- 43% of respondents apply a self-defined metadata schema to describe resources in their services, and 23% plan to do so. [1]
- 44% of respondents have described specific mappings or extensions their team or organization has developed. [2]

- 79% of survey respondents answered that they are involved in groups or forums that focus on metadata issues, including discussions on standards, quality, and enhancements. [2]

Figure 1: Which metadata schemas are currently used in your repository/repositories for PID registration? [2]

Limitations and Future Work

A limitation in the design of the 2024 survey was that responses on standards could only be mapped to consortia and not to specific services (e.g., repositories) within consortia. Therefore, the next phase of the project will require further work, including online research and contacting repository managers to map standards directly to repositories, if feasible. Further steps also include compiling a list of metadata mappings that will be added into the catalog, and updating the catalog with additional standards. Those tasks are in line with the tasks T2.1.1. and T2.1.2. from the *Concept for Metadata Interoperability and Harmonization* for the integration phase [3]. Hence, the metadata standards catalog will be treated as a living document, to be updated periodically with new versions.

Finally, it is important to note that both current and future versions of the metadata catalog will only include a subset of standards used in NFDI. This limitation is due to the vast number of repositories within NFDI, making a comprehensive roadmap impractical.

Further Resources

Further resources in the context of metadata standards are the [RDA Metadata Standards Catalog](#) compiled by the *RDA Metadata Standards Catalog WG* and the [List of Metadata Standards by the Digital Curation Center \(DDC\)](#), for example. An overview of metadata mappings is available at the [RDA Index of Mappings](#), and a general knowledge base on metadata standards is e.g. available at [NFDI4Chem](#).

References

[1] Hagemann-Wilholt, S. (2023, February 13). PID4NFDI: Survey on PID Practices. Main results. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7635791>

[2] El-Gebali, S., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Böhm, J., & Kahlert, T. (2024). D1.1 Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277479>

[3] El-Gebali, S. (2024). Concepts for metadata interoperability, harmonization and technical integration of PID infrastructure. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506138>